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To cite this article before publication: Dominika Jochcová *et al* 2024 *J. Opt.* in press <https://doi.org/10.1088/2040-8986/ad9619>

Manuscript version: Accepted Manuscript

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Power output optimization in complex laser systems by means of polarization control

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Compiled November 5, 2024

Recently, the polarimetric method for thermally-induced polarization changes driven power losses (TIPCL) mitigation in complex laser systems has been developed. However, the final optimization relied on the four-parameter numerical process. This article provides a fully analytical direct calculation alternative to this optimization process. The validity of this approach is demonstrated on the previously published data from pulsed laser system Bivoj/DiPOLE100. The new approach provides a deeper insight into the polarimetric method for TIPCL suppression and also brings a more precise, reliable, and faster alternative to the numerical process used earlier.

INTRODUCTION

A recent development on the field of high-energy high-average-power (HE-HAP) pulsed laser systems [1–4] boosted an urgent need of the thermo-optic phenomena suppression. The thermal-stress-induced birefringence (TSIB), as one of these phenomena, was reported in most of these laser systems. The volumetric heat load generated in the laser amplifiers and other optical components give rise to the distortions of the passing-through laser beam. Among them, TSIB induces non-uniform polarization changes across the beams' cross-section. Such effect can significantly decrease the efficiency of the polarization-sensitive phenomena, e.g. higher harmonics conversion [2, 5–7], optical parametric amplification [8] or make impossible polarization-sensitive experiments. In combination with a linear diattenuator, typically polarizer, a significant loss of energy also occurs accompanied by the intensity profile change. Such loss of energy can theoretically reach up to 50%. However, the typical values reported in the above literature from the HE-HAP laser systems lie, from our experience, usually between 20% and 40%.

The reduction or compensation of TSIB is therefore one of the key techniques needed for efficient operation of HE-HAP lasers. The reduction of TSIB is mostly realized during the design phase of the laser system and contains the techniques like proper materials choice, optical components geometry optimization, or cooling system design [9–15]. On the other hand, the compensation techniques are mostly integrable into already built systems and relies on the employment of some additional optical components, or by proper choice of the polarization state of the seeding light. The traditional compensation technique using reciprocal polarization rotator which works very well in simple systems [16–18] fails in the case of large lasers containing many additional optical elements next to the amplifiers. So far there

are just a couple of sources reporting the TSIB compensation by proper polarization state selection [19, 20]. The most advanced and efficient technique so far is a polarimetry assisted approach presented in [21].

The compensation method assisted by polarimetric measurement led to the formulation of the optimization problem essential for a successful usage of such method. This optimization step can be formulated as follows: *one is searching for the uniform polarization state suffering the lowest distortion when it propagates through defined non-uniformly polarizing optical system in the sense that its part blocked by the output elliptical polarizer carries minimal energy. The procedure should also determine the parameters of such output elliptical polarizer.* The optimisation process is therefore searching for four parameters of the system. The azimuth and the phase delay of the input polarization and the same couple of parameters of the output polarizer. So far, the problem has been successfully solved numerically in [21]. The numerical solution is, however, relatively slow and does not provide any more general insight into the problem. For example, the ideal configuration for a simple systems for which an analytical solution TSIB is available, e.g. heated cylindrically symmetrical rod amplifier, cannot be deduced on the basis of the numerical solution. Also the limits of usability of such optimization are not quite clear from the numerical solution. All these uncertainties led to the searching for an analytical solution presented in this work.

METHODS

As reported in [21], the Mueller-matrix polarimetry based method of TIPCL reduction led to the decrease of the power loss from 33% to 9%, and after the more precise measurement even down to 3% [6]. It was also shown that the optical setup

used for the compensation is equivalent to the arrangement in which the whole amplifier chain is placed between two properly chosen elliptical polarizers. Such equivalent scheme is shown in Fig. 1. The azimuth angles α_1, α_2 and the phase delays ϕ_1, ϕ_2

Fig. 1. The schematic of generalized polarizer-analyzer setup for TIPCL evaluation; distorting optical system \mathbf{M} is placed between two elliptical polarizers \mathbf{P} .

are then subject to the above mentioned optimization process which is within this work transformed into the direct calculation of these four parameters. Such an approach makes the optimization much faster, precise, and also provides the novel insight into the process of the compensation itself.

The analysis of the problem formulated at the beginning of this section is addressed in 3 gradual steps. The first step specifies the parameters of the output elliptical polarizer for a given general input polarization state. The parameters of the output polarizer are, in this case, expressed as functions of the input polarizer characteristics. The second step provides the values of the input polarizer parameters suffering the minimal polarization distortion for a given optical system. The third step summarizes the formulation of the method in the Mueller calculus, thus allowing direct connection of the developed optimization method with an experimental Mueller matrix of the studied optical system obtained from the polarimetric measurement.

OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

Step one: output polarizer

The first step of the process is dedicated to the specification of the output elliptical polarizer for the fixed input polarization state, the schematic describing the problem is shown in Fig. 2. Let us use the standard parametrization of the Jones vector representing the totally-polarized input state of light as $E(\alpha, \phi) = [E_x, E_y]^T = [\cos \alpha e^{i\phi}, \sin \alpha]^T$, where $\alpha \in (0, \frac{\pi}{2})$ is the azimuth of the polarization ellipse and $\phi \in (-\pi, \pi)$ is the phase delay between orthogonal-base linear polarizations. Let us assume that the considered optical system is generally birefringent i.e. represented as a non-depolarizing optical system, possessing no diattenuation. The equivalence theorems of the Jones calculus proved in [22, 23] allow us to represent the above-defined optical system by a single unitary Jones matrix $\mathbf{M}(x, y)$ with transversely (with respect to the beam propagation direction) dependant elements $m_i(x, y)$ and $\varphi(x, y)$ parameterized as

$$\mathbf{M} = e^{i\varphi/2} \begin{bmatrix} m_1 & m_2 \\ -m_2^* & m_1^* \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $|m_1|^2 + |m_2|^2 = 1$. It should be noted that isotropic absorption or amplification does not influence the polarization state and therefore it does not have to be taken into consideration. The output polarization state, leaving the optical system $\mathbf{M}(x, y)$, is described by a transversely non-uniform Jones vector $E_3 = E_3(\alpha(x, y), \phi(x, y))$. The output polarizer $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_2, \phi_2)$

(see Fig. 1) is represented by an orthogonal projector to the state $E(\alpha_2, \phi_2)$, represented by a Hermitian idempotent matrix

$$\mathbf{P}(\alpha_2, \phi_2) = E(\alpha_2, \phi_2) E^\dagger(\alpha_2, \phi_2), \quad (2)$$

where E^\dagger is the conjugate transpose of the vector E . For practical reasons, let us divide the output transverse plane into a set of discrete $N \times M$ points and consider a constant Jones vector in each point of these node points. This leads to the discretized quantities $E_3(\alpha(x, y), \phi(x, y)) \rightarrow E_3(\alpha(x_i, y_j), \phi(x_i, y_j)) \equiv E_3(x_i, y_j)$, where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$. This discretization is advantageous for the work with the experimental data, which are inherently represented by a discrete set of values. Also the numerical approaches, which are mostly used for the evaluation of the induced birefringence effects, are typically performed on a discrete grid. Each point (x_i, y_j) represents an area upon which the Jones vector is considered to be constant. When light passes the output polarizer, the intensity of the passed-through beam is determined by $I(x_i, y_j) = |\mathbf{P}E_3(x_i, y_j)|^2$. For the further development of the method, it is beneficial to define the sum output intensity of the beam I_{tot} over all node points as

$$I_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M |\mathbf{P}E_3(x_i, y_j)|^2. \quad (3)$$

The objective is to maximize the sum intensity I_{tot} by the selection of an appropriate output polarizer \mathbf{P} . It can be derived (see Appendix A) that there exists an equivalent expression of Eq. (3) in the form

$$I_{tot} = \mathbf{P}^\dagger \mathbf{D} \mathbf{P}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{P} stands for the eigenstate of the polarizer \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{D} is the matrix defined as

$$\mathbf{D} \equiv \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M E_3(x_i, y_j) E_3(x_i, y_j)^\dagger. \quad (5)$$

\mathbf{D} is a finite sum of Hermitian idempotent matrices that represent projectors onto output polarization states. Consequently, \mathbf{D} is Hermitian, although it is generally not idempotent, thus representing a general diattenuator (also called partial polarizer). Let d_1 and d_2 be the eigenvalues of \mathbf{D} . The output sum intensity obviously varies with the choice of the output polarizer \mathbf{P} . However, the eigenvalues d_1 and d_2 serve as limits on I_{tot} ensuring that I_{tot} consistently lies within the interval $I_{tot} \in (d_2, d_1)$ where, without loss of generality, $d_{1,2}$ fulfill $d_1 \geq d_2$. Let us denote the eigenstates of \mathbf{D} as $D_{1,2}$, i.e. $\mathbf{D}D_{1,2} = d_{1,2}D_{1,2}$. Apparently, maximization of the output power of the laser beam can be achieved by the proper choice of the eigenstate of the output polarizer \mathbf{P} as $\mathbf{P} \equiv D_1$. Minimal dimensionless depolarization loss, according to its common laser physics definition as a ratio of power leakage through the output polarizer to the total power, η_{min} is related to the eigenvalues of \mathbf{D} as

$$\eta_{min} = \frac{d_2}{MN} = \left(1 - \frac{d_1}{MN}\right), \quad (6)$$

see Appendix B for step-by-step derivation of the Eq. 6.

Step two: input polarizer

The second step of the process deals with searching for the optimal parameters of the input elliptical polarizer $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$ which produces the input polarization state for the studied optical

Fig. 2. The schematic of the output polarizer selection process; input polarizer is fixed to transmit only linear horizontal states; based on the polarization profile of the NUTP output beam $E_3(x, y)$ emerging from the amplifier the depolarization loss η differs with the choice of the output polarizer eigenstate P . The sense of rotation of the polarization ellipse is color-separated by green (clockwise) and red (anti-clockwise).

system. A widely used method for representing the polarization of quasi-monochromatic waves is based on the coherency matrix [24]. However, the coherency matrix representing fully polarized, partially correlated fields with a spatially varying polarization state can also be constructed [25] in a similar way. In terms of the spatially varying elements of the Jones vector, the polarization matrix \mathbf{J} is defined as

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle E_x E_x^* \rangle & \langle E_x E_y^* \rangle \\ \langle E_y E_x^* \rangle & \langle E_y E_y^* \rangle \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} j_{xx} & j_{xy} \\ j_{yx} & j_{yy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where the angular brackets represent the spatial mean value over the cross-section of the beam. Thus, considering $E \equiv E_3$, the \mathbf{J} -matrix characterizes the statistical properties of the spatially resolved polarization state, i.e. the non-uniformly totally polarized (NUTP) beam emerging from the optical medium [26]. Let E_2 be the polarization state entering the optical system, thus $E_2 = E_2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$ is the eigenstate of input polarizer $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$. The NUTP beam E_3 leaving the optical system is given as $E_3(x, y) = \mathbf{M}(x, y) E_2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$. By the substitution for \mathbf{M} from (1) and for the eigenvector of $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$, one gets

$$E_3 = e^{i\varphi/2} \begin{bmatrix} m_1 \cos \alpha_1 e^{i\phi_1} + m_2 \sin \alpha_1 \\ -m_2^* \cos \alpha_1 e^{i\phi_1} + m_1^* \sin \alpha_1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Taking into account that the NUTP beam represents the mixture of many polarization states over the cross-section of the beam, the spatial degree of polarization p can be defined for a NUTP beam. It should be noted here that from the point of view of the studied problem, the beams with an arbitrary spatial distribution of the polarization states over the beam are indistinguishable as long as the total area occupied by every single polarization state remains the same. In other words, every two NUTP beams with their spatial distribution will lead to exactly the same resulting power loss and therefore they can be exchanged freely. One of these equivalent NUTP beams is always the one with a random spatial distribution of the desired polarization states composition. Such a beam is the one for which it makes sense to define the degree of polarization analogously to the partially polarized light. The degree of polarization p can be then expressed directly from the polarization matrix (8) as [27]

$$p^2 = \text{Tr}^2 \mathbf{J} - 4 \text{Det} \mathbf{J}. \quad (10)$$

Since \mathbf{M} was assumed to be the unitary Jones matrix, the trace of \mathbf{J} -matrix is identically equal to unity $\text{Tr} \mathbf{J} = \langle |m_1|^2 + |m_2|^2 \rangle = 1$.

The figure of merit of the studied problem is the quantity usually called the depolarization loss η . When obtained from the experimental data, the depolarization loss is calculated as the ratio of the power leakage through the optical system placed between crossed polarizers to the total power transmitted through the optical system without these polarizers. The depolarization loss η is directly connected to the spatial degree of polarization. Let us consider I_p and I_{np} be the completely polarized and completely unpolarized intensity compounds of the beam, respectively, i.e. $I = I_p + I_{np}$. When a beam is transmitted through the output polarizer $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_2, \phi_2)$, the transmittance $T(I_p) = 1$ for a proper choice of the eigenstate (α_2, ϕ_2) . In contrary, $T(I_{np}) = 1/2$ for an arbitrary choice of $\mathbf{P}(\alpha_2, \phi_2)$. Consequently, maximal transmittance is given by

$$T(I_p + I_{np}) = 1 - \frac{I_{np}}{2(I_{np} + I_p)}. \quad (11)$$

Since $p = I_p / (I_p + I_{np})$, the depolarization loss can be expressed as

$$\eta = (1 - T) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - p). \quad (12)$$

The depolarization loss η reaches its minimum as p approaches its maximal value. Substituting (9) into (8) and (10) and simplifying the expression, one obtains

$$p^2 = 1 - \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos 4\alpha_1)(\mu - 2 \cos 2\phi_1 \Re\{v\} + 2 \sin 2\phi_1 \Im\{v\}) - 2 \sin 4\alpha_1 (\cos \phi_1 \Re\{\xi\} + \sin \phi_1 \Im\{\xi\}) - o(1 + \cos 4\alpha_1) - \lambda, \quad (13)$$

where symbols $\Re\{\}$, $\Im\{\}$ stand for real and imaginary part, respectively. Optical system parameters λ, μ, v, ξ, o are given as

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= 2(|m_1|^2 \langle |m_2|^2 \rangle), \\ \mu &= \langle |m_1|^2 \rangle^2 + \langle |m_2|^2 \rangle^2 - 2|\langle m_1 m_2^* \rangle|^2 - |\langle m_1^2 \rangle|^2 - |\langle m_2^2 \rangle|^2, \\ v &= \langle m_1 m_2^* \rangle^2 - \langle m_1^2 \rangle \langle m_2^2 \rangle, \\ \xi &= \langle m_1^* \rangle \langle m_1 m_2 \rangle - \langle m_1^* m_2^* \rangle \langle m_2^2 \rangle + \langle |m_2|^2 - |m_1|^2 \rangle \langle m_2 m_1^* \rangle, \\ o &= \langle |m_1|^2 \rangle \langle |m_2|^2 \rangle - 2|\langle m_1 m_2 \rangle|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The squared spatial degree of polarization p^2 (13) is a function of two input polarization state variables (α_1, ϕ_1) and parameters of the optical system (14) which are fixed by the studied optical system. Let us examine the stationary points of $p^2 = p^2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$ by the search for the zeros of its gradient $\nabla p^2 = \mathbf{0}$. After the substitution $x \equiv \tan \phi_1$, the gradient equation is transformed into a 5th order polynomial in x while α_1 can be excluded from the equations. Two roots of this polynomial are always equal $\pm i$. This fact allows the decrease of the order of the polynomial to 3rd $\sum_{i=0}^3 a_i x^i = 0$, where a_i are the parameters depending exclusively on the optical system parameters. Full expressions for a_i are provided in (7). $\Re\{\}$ and $\Im\{\}$ mark real and imaginary part, respectively. λ, μ, v, ξ, o are the optical system parameters introduced in (14). Taking into account the periodicity of $p^2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$, its extremal values should be found in the interval $(0, \frac{\pi}{2}) \times (-\pi, \pi)$. These values then define the optimal polarization state which suffers the lowest possible depolarization loss.

$$\begin{aligned}
a_0 &= \Im\{v\}\Re\{\xi\}(-\frac{1}{2}\mu + o - \Re\{v\}) + \Im\{\xi\}(\Im\{v\}^2 - \Re\{\xi\}^2) \\
a_1 &= \Im\{v\}\Im\{\xi\}(\frac{1}{2}\mu - o - 3\Re\{v\}) + \Re\{v\}\Re\{\xi\}(2\Re\{v\} + \mu - 2o) + \Re\{\xi\}(2\Im\{\xi\}^2 - \Re\{\xi\}^2 - \Im\{v\}^2) \\
a_2 &= \Im\{\xi\}(-\Im\{v\}^2 - \Im\{\xi\}^2 + 2\Re\{\xi\}^2) + \Im\{v\}\Re\{\xi\}(\frac{1}{2}\mu - o + 3\Re\{v\}) + \Im\{\xi\}\Re\{v\}(2o - \mu + 2\Re\{v\}) \\
a_3 &= \Im\{\xi\}\Im\{v\}(-\frac{1}{2}\mu + o + \Re\{v\}) + \Re\{\xi\}(\Im\{v\}^2 - \Im\{\xi\}^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Fig. 3. a)-b) The density of states for output polarization vector $E_3 = E_{out}(x, y)$ in polarimetric coordinates (α, ϕ) for input linear vertical polarization a) and optimized input polarization state b); c) Polarization pattern of the cross-section of the output NUTP beam; for input linear vertical polarization and d) for optimal input polarization, the sense of rotation of the polarization ellipse is color-separated by green (clockwise) and red (anti-clockwise); e) Spatially-resolved Mueller matrix of the laser system obtained from polarimetric measurement and f) its' spatial average $\langle \mathcal{M} \rangle$; g) visualisation of the $p^2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$ function calculated for the system, yellow point signifies the maximum; h) blue ellipsoidal surface represents solution of $S_{out} = \mathcal{M}S_{in}$, where the yellow arrow corresponds to the maximum noted in $p^2(\alpha_1, \phi_1)$ visualisation in g), the red arrow lying on the Poincaré's sphere corresponds to an optimal input polarization state.

Step three: optimization in the Mueller calculus

In the third step of the process, the part of the calculation is transferred to the Mueller matrix formalism which is more preferable for the processing of the experimental data. The above derived technique will be transformed from the Jones notation to Mueller matrices. Such step makes this technique more applicable to the experimentally obtained results. Let us define the W vector, which characterizes the general fully polarized state, as a Kronecker product of two Jones vectors in the form used in the previous sections

$$W = E^* \otimes E. \tag{15}$$

The similar transformation can be done with the Jones matrix \mathbf{M} given by (1). Since the elements of \mathbf{M} are already the functions of the spatial coordinates, one should, similarly to (14), apply the spatial mean value represented by the angular brackets. Let us denote the resulting matrix as \mathcal{C} ,

$$\mathcal{C} = \langle \mathbf{M}^* \otimes \mathbf{M} \rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \langle |m_1|^2 \rangle & \langle m_1^* m_2 \rangle & c_{12}^* & \langle |m_2|^2 \rangle \\ -\langle m_1^* m_2 \rangle & \langle m_1^* m_1 \rangle & -\langle m_2^* m_2 \rangle & -c_{21} \\ c_{21}^* & c_{23}^* & c_{22}^* & -c_{21}^* \\ c_{14} & -c_{12} & -c_{12}^* & c_{11} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{16}$$

The connection to the experimentally preferred Mueller matrix notation is now becoming more obvious while there is a simple connection between the W vector and the corresponding Stokes vector S and also between the \mathcal{C} matrix and the Mueller matrix \mathcal{M} .

$$S = \mathcal{A}W^*, \quad \mathcal{M} = \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M} \otimes \mathbf{M}^*)\mathcal{A}^{-1}, \tag{17}$$

where \mathcal{A} matrix is defined as $\mathcal{A} = [\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3]^T$, where σ_i are the Pauli matrices written as a column vector [28]. The spatial mean value can be then easily applied to the Mueller matrix $\langle \mathcal{M} \rangle = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{C}^*\mathcal{A}^{-1}$. The squared degree of polarization (10) can be, in this case, calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
p^2 &= (q_1 + q_4)^2 - 4(q_1q_4 - q_2q_3) = \\
&= (q_1 - q_4)^2 + 4q_2q_3,
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where $Q \equiv CW = [q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4]^T$ is a function of the input polarization parameters (α_1, ϕ_1) and \mathcal{C} is calculated from the experimentally obtained Mueller matrix \mathcal{M} . This formulation offers a straightforward means to compute the degree of polarization by direct utilizing the results from the experimental characterization of the optical system in the form of the Mueller matrix \mathcal{M} .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The above derived procedure will be demonstrated on the results presented in [21]. The subject to the spatially resolved Mueller matrix measurement was a last stage of the power amplifiers of the 100J/10Hz pulsed laser system "Bivoj/DiPOLE100" operated at HiLASE Centre, Czech Republic. The resulting Mueller matrix, presented also in [21], is shown in Fig. 3 e). In the original reference, the numerical four parameter optimization has been used to find the ideal adjustment of the waveplates surrounding the amplifier chain. Let us demonstrate the direct calculation method on this example. The optimal input polarization state can be directly computed from the Mueller matrix $\mathcal{M}(x, y)$ (Fig. 3 e-f) of the amplifier chain by finding the maximum of p^2 (18). The p^2 as a function of the input polarization in the polarimetric coordinates (α, ϕ) is shown in Fig. 3 g). The polarization profile of the NUTP beam leaving the amplifier chain is then shown in Fig. 3 c-d). Fig. 3 c) demonstrates the NUTP beam leaving the amplifier with the vertical polarization on the input while the right hand side profile Fig. 3 d) is a NUTP beam produced by the amplifier from the ideal input polarization which can be read out from p^2 function as $(\alpha_1, \phi_1) = (0.584, -1.772)$ rad. The degree of purity of the polarization state can be also well visualized by the density of polarization states in the polarimetric coordinates (α, ϕ) as shown in Fig. 3 a)-b). The transformation from the spatial to the polarimetric coordinates has been applied. Better localization of the polarization states in the second beam allows more effective transmission by means of a properly chosen elliptical polarizer. The knowledge of the output NUTP beam allow us to construct the \mathbf{D} operator according to (5). The output polarizer providing maximum transmission is the one whose eigenstate is exactly the same as the eigenstate of the \mathbf{D} operator corresponding to the larger eigennumber d_1 . The polarimetric coordinates of this eigenstate results to $(\alpha_2, \phi_2) = (0.693, 0.997)$ rad. Together with the coordinates of the input state these values are in excellent agreement with the ones obtained in [21]. Considering the time demands, the computational time is reduced from tens of minutes (typically around 1 hour) to less than one second computation in case of the analytical solution with a common PC.

Laser rod

The above technique can also benefit from the existence of known analytical solution for the rod geometry. Assuming the thermally loaded laser rod made of cubic crystal in crystallographic orientation [111] under plain-strain approximation with radially symmetrical top-hat pump and strictly radial heat flow, the spatially resolved Jones matrix of the medium can be derived [29, 30]. In such case the above method can provide a proof that in this particular case the best possible input polarization is always linear and the worst possible value of TIPCL for optimized input will always be lower than 30.3%. Normalized \mathbf{D} matrix can be constructed by continuous transition of Eq. (5).

$$\mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{\pi R^2} \int_0^R \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \mathbf{P}_{out}(\alpha_{out}, \phi_{out}, r, \varphi) r dr d\varphi, \quad (19)$$

where radial coordinates used here (r, φ) are beneficial in description of the rod geometry; R denotes both the radius of the laser rod which equals to the radius of the pump top-hat beam, $\mathbf{P}_{out} = E_{out} E_{out}^\dagger$, where $E_{out}(r, \varphi) = \mathbf{M}(r, \varphi) E_{in}$. Similarly, the spacial averaging is estimated by

$$\langle m_i \rangle = \frac{1}{\pi R^2} \int_0^R \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} m_i(r, \varphi) r dr d\varphi. \quad (20)$$

The p^2 function from (13) simplifies because certain optical system parameters introduced in (14) are zeros; $\Re\{\zeta\} = \Im\{\zeta\} = \Im\{v\} = 0$. An expression for the minimal normalized eigennumber $\eta \equiv d_2$ (depolarization loss) can be derived for the optimal case (linear input polarization) and the worst case in terms of effective depolarization compensation (circular input polarization)

$$\eta_{circ} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sin aR^2}{aR^2} \right), \quad \eta_{lin} = \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{\sin aR^2}{aR^2} \right), \quad (21)$$

where parameter a is determined by the material properties, geometry and is proportional to the pump power [29, 30]. From Fig. 4 b) notice that the input polarization which minimizes the depolarization loss is arbitrarily oriented linear polarization (corresponds to states in the (α, ϕ) coordinates located on edges of the plotting region). Circular polarization on the other hand, maximizes the losses, which oscillate around 50%. Regardless the the pump power and material properties represented by the parameter a , losses for the laser rod can always be reduced under $\max(\eta_{lin}) = \frac{2+3\pi}{12\pi} \approx 0.303$ (see Fig. 4 a)). Lines at 0.5 and 0.25 indicate the limit value of η_{circ} and η_{lin} in the expression Eq. 21 when the parameter a approaches infinity.

Fig. 4. The graph of calculated depolarization loss η as a function of the a parameter; **a)** for optimal (linear) input polarization and circular polarization ($R = 0.4$ m); **b)** p^2 function for the laser rod ($a = 5000$ rad·m $^{-2}$, $R = 0.01$ m).

CONCLUSIONS

Effective management of depolarization losses is essential in high-average-power laser systems. The availability of an analytical solution for optimization offers an efficient alternative to time-consuming numerical calculations. Future efforts will focus on the general automation of depolarization-loss mitigation. A significant outcome of the framework developed here is the ability to replace spatially resolved Mueller-matrix polarimetry with power-only measurements. This method has the potential to accelerate the optimization process and can be easily implemented in similar laser systems that experience depolarization losses.

A. Appendix

The most suitable way how to derive the transition from the output polarizer applied to the NUTP beam produced by some optical system (4) is by using the Dirac notation applied to the Jones vectors and matrices. Let

$$E_3(x_i, y_j) \rightarrow |E_{ij}\rangle, \quad P \rightarrow |P\rangle, \quad \mathbf{P} \rightarrow |P\rangle\langle P|,$$

consequently, (3) takes the form

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M |\mathbf{P}|E_{ij}\rangle|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M ||P\rangle\langle P|E_{ij}\rangle|^2, \quad (22)$$

expanding the formula and considering the normalization $\langle P|P \rangle = 1$:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M \langle E_{ij}|P \rangle \langle P|P \rangle \langle P|E_{ij} \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M \langle P|E_{ij} \rangle \langle E_{ij}|P \rangle, \quad (23)$$

the linearity of the scalar product allows for the change in the order of summation and multiplication

$$\langle P| \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M |E_{ij}\rangle \langle E_{ij}| \right) |P \rangle = \langle P| \mathbf{D} |P \rangle. \quad (24)$$

Formula (24) directly defines the formal partial polarizer \mathbf{D} .

B. Appendix

Equation (6) can be derived from the the matrix of a projector to the i -th output state E_i , where for simplicity, the summation is taken over a single index. Let the Jones vectors $E_1 = [\cos \alpha_1 e^{i\phi_1}, \sin \alpha_1]^T$ and $E_2 = [\cos \alpha_2 e^{i\phi_2}, \sin \alpha_2]^T$ are two different output states with discretization of the output plane $NM = 2$. Projector to the output state can be expressed as

$$E_i E_i^\dagger = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha_i & \cos \alpha_i \sin \alpha_i e^{i\phi_i} \\ \cos \alpha_i \sin \alpha_i e^{-i\phi_i} & \sin^2 \alpha_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

Considering two output states $NM = 2$, the \mathbf{D} matrix is given by $\mathbf{D} = E_1 E_1^\dagger + E_2 E_2^\dagger$. The trace of a matrix is a sum of the eigenvalues, $\text{Tr} \mathbf{D} = d_1 + d_2$, which leads to

$$d_1 + d_2 = \text{Tr} \mathbf{D} = \cos^2 \alpha_1 + \cos^2 \alpha_2 + \sin^2 \alpha_1 + \sin^2 \alpha_2 = 2. \quad (26)$$

Thus, η_{min} fulfills

$$1 = \frac{d_1 + d_2}{MN} \implies \eta_{min} \equiv \frac{d_2}{MN} = 1 - \frac{d_1}{MN}. \quad (27)$$

Similar procedure can be applied to arbitrary discretization MN .

Funding. European Regional Development Fund and the state budget of the Czech Republic project HiLASE CoE (CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/15_006/0000674); LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573. Student Grant Competition of CTU in Prague (No. SGS22/185/OHK4/3T/14).

Acknowledgments. This work is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the state budget of the Czech Republic project HiLASE CoE (CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/15_006/0000674); LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573. This research was supported by Student Grant Competition of CTU in Prague (No. SGS22/185/OHK4/3T/14).

Disclosures. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability. No data were generated or analyzed in the presented research.

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